

“AI Based Cost Optimized Waste Segregation System Using Image Processing”

Vahid M. Jamadar¹, Hemant K. Shete², Suyash Nalawade³, Pranita Shedage⁴, Karan Chavare⁵, Pranoti Thorat⁶, Chaitanya Bhosale⁷

Assistant Prof., AGTI's Dr. Daulatrao Aher College of Engineering, Karad, India^{1,2}

B.Tech Student, Mechanical Engineering, AGTI's Dr. Daulatrao Aher College of Engineering
Karad, Maharashtra, India^{3,4,5,6,7}

Abstract: Improper waste segregate leads to number of problems of environmental pollution and Economical impact. Handling waste is becoming more complicated and expensive due to population growth. This research introduces a cost-efficient method for waste segregation using image processing. Project approach influence computer vision and machine learning algorithms to streamlines the automation of identifying types of waste. This project aims to reduce human effort by using AI. The main purpose of this sorting system is to reduce amount of mixed waste going to landfill. If the waste is segregates before it reaching the landfill, the overall amount of waste will be reduced. This waste segregation management system mainly designed for municipal and office purpose. It segregates waste like plastic, paper, cloth and organic materials.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Image Processing, Waste Segregation System, Cost Optimization, Smart Waste Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Waste is not segregate properly led to number of problems of pollution and economic impact. This project purpose to be minimize human effort by using AI. The main purpose of this sorting system is to reduce amount of waste going to landfill. If the waste is segregate before it reaches landfill, the amount of waste will be reduced at landfill. This waste segregation management system mainly made for municipal purpose. To counter this issue, develop a waste segregation management system by using image processing. It segregates industrial waste (Dry waste) like paper, plastic, organic and cloth waste. It's also act as a smart bin. which includes camera, microcontroller, sensor and motors. This system segregates dry waste very neat and clean. In this waste segregation system camera used for capture an image of waste. After that camera gives signal to microcontroller for detecting the type of waste. The signals from the camera are fed to the motor by the microcontroller. To detect the waste that is going to fall in the which compartments. Sensor detects filled compartments and gives the signals by using colour coding. Red, Yellow and Green LED are used to indicates how full compartment of waste.

2. COMPONENTS:

- Camera – ESP32 used for capturing image of waste items.
- Microcontroller – ESP32 microcontroller used to gather all input from camera and controlling all system.
- Sensor – Proximity sensor for sensing the level of waste items in containers.
- Motor – NEMA 17 motor rotates wooden plate that help to separate waste material based on type of waste.
- Motor Driver – It used for control and manage power supply to motor.
- Containers – Acrylic containers are used for easy to check level of waste items and looks aesthetic.

3. CONCEPTUAL CAD MODEL AND BLOCK DIAGRAM:

4. WORKING:

- Overview - The main purpose of this system is to reduce the human effort with the help of automation. Also, reduce time and cost of the system for segregating.
- Image Processing – Camera (ESP Cam) captures an image of waste items which are rests at hopper and flapper plate. This image has inputs to the AI system for processing and classification work.
- Pre-processing – After the image processing microcontroller (ESP32) to gather all input from camera and controlling all system. Camera sends image to microcontroller and microcontroller perform segmentation of this waste images. Microcontroller give signal to motor through motor driver for which type waste goes fall on which container of this system.
- Mechanism – Hopper placed at top of the model, waste items fall on hopper and rests at flapper plate at that time camera capture an image. After pre-processing microcontroller gives signal to motor and motor rotate at specific angle. The motor rotates to the wooden plate and place the container at the bottom of hopper opening.

- Output – Sensor is placed at near to containers. Sensor senses the containers waste level and gives signal to microcontroller. LED lights are used in this system for indicating the level of waste at containers with the help of RED, YELLOW and GREEN lights. After taking signal from sensor, microcontroller send signals and LED lights emits.

5. CALCULATION OF MOTOR:

- Total weight of waste as per container volume -
 1. Plastic waste = 0.614 kg
 2. Organic waste = 1.2 kg
 3. Cloth waste = 0.25 kg
 4. Paper waste = 0.2 kg
 - Total weight of waste = 2.264 kg
 - Weight of base (wooden) plate = 1.37 kg
 - Weight of containers = 0.485 kg
- Overall weight of components on motor = Total weight of waste + base plate + containers

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(mass)} &= 2.264 + 1.37 + 0.485 \\ &= 4.119 \text{ kg} \end{aligned}$$
- Motor Shaft radius = 5 mm = 0.5 cm
- Torque = Mass \times Radius \times FOS

$$= 4.119 \times 0.25 \times 1.5$$

Torque = 1.5446 kgcm.

6. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The developed AI-based waste segregation system successfully classified waste into categories such as plastic, paper, organic and unidentified using image processing techniques. The system was trained using a dataset of labelled waste images and achieved an accuracy of 60-70% on the test dataset. The model real-time testing demonstrated efficient classification with an average processing time of 10-15 seconds per image.

7. CONCLUSION:

The development and implementation of an AI- based waste segregation system offers a significant advancement in waste management practices. This system helps to minimizing human effort with the help of AI also, reduce mix waste in landfill and cost for segregation. We can reduce the environmental impact of waste and help move toward a circular economy. Many devices have also been designed in order to carry on this process efficiently. Hardware components and software components used along with various algorithm to achieve the output. This technology is scalable and adaptable to different requirements.

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